

THE DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH IDIOMS

Puşcaşu A.,

Technical University of Moldova, University Assistant

Şişianu A.

Technical University of Moldova, University Assistant

Abstract

The idioms are an indispensable part of the English language, thus becoming an essential moment whilst teaching-learning the English language. But, the process of teaching and learning English idioms has always been a challenging one and requires a lot of experience and creativity, since they are not always easy to understand, remember and use. This study aims to investigate the perspective of English teachers on idioms in language teaching and learning. It assumes that the major points that make idioms such an obstacle to English learners are: a) the complex structure of idioms; and b) the idiom comprehension. During this very study we used the meta-synthesis method to find some common results and to identify overall trends whereas teaching-learning English idioms. So, we've come to the conclusion that a systematic review of the grounds beyond the difficulties in teaching-learning the English idioms could be of a great aid.

Keywords: analysability, equivalence, idiomatic, idiomaticity, metaphoricity.

1. Introduction

Every language retains idioms with the specialized features in linguistic forms. The idiom is functional and is one of the manifold figurative speeches in linguistics. It is commonly being used by the people of a particular region or country for informal and formal, spoken and written purposes. Idioms are not only a part of language, but also they are the part of universal communication. We use idioms for theoretical purposes, and if we categorize idioms, they can be used in different ways for different purposes.

The English language is very rich in idiomatic expressions. They are everywhere! In order to preserve humorousness and originality of the English language idioms should be learned and used in English. So, we can say, that it's a duty of a teacher to acquire idioms and to become able to teach them in spite of the difficulties that are encountered during this process. Although idioms and most figurative expressions are used extensively by native speakers in all form of discourse, they seem to be often a neglected topic in schools. English teachers sometimes try to simplify the English language to their students and most of the focus is directed to grammar rules as they find idioms hard to comprehend or dispose. That's why, this lack of understanding of idiomatic expressions then can lead to communication failure. In consequence, we consider that the problem of identifying the difficulties in teaching-learning English idioms is a very important and interesting one.

This article gives a broad perspective on difficulties in teaching and learning English idioms. The purpose of this didactical research is to identify the difficulties in teaching-learning English idioms, thereby to make this process less troublesome and challenging. Overall, this work analyzes, interprets and draws the difficulties that appear in the process of teaching-learning English idioms. Moreover, this paper looks at and explains the reasons behind the difficulties of English idioms that learners encounter in listening, reading, and speaking.

After a systemic review of different studies and a meta-synthesis of a lot of works about English idioms, we can definitely mention that idioms play an important

role in English language studying due to their frequency and, which is more, that English idioms are difficult to understand, remember and use because of their complex nature. *Noodle on* that thought for a while, and you'll understand why it's hard for our students to make *heads or tails out of* any idiom [4].

2. Materials and Methods

During the study there were consulted a great number of books, dictionaries, and articles on this topic. In this very study the systemic review of multiple theories of idioms was tried. By combining different studies and ideas of idiom structure and meaning, we have aimed to come up with some new useful results in order to identify the difficulties while teaching-learning the English idioms. In fact, after all particular attention was paid to the meta-synthesis method of research, that is the basic tool of the work. Thereby, after a long qualitative study, we have managed to combine all our findings and then, to make known the data of multiple studies to summarize common results and to point out overall trends.

3. Results

3.1 Defining the Term of Idiom

Many linguists claim that it is practically impossible to produce a general definition of idiom that would cover all its features and attributes. The word "Idiom" is of Greek origin and means "standing apart on its own". An idiom, then, is a construction which stands apart from the rest of the language on account of this irregularity and examination would show that they are almost all of a popular rather than a literary character, belonging to the spoken rather than the written language. Idioms are considered figures of speech, which are defined as "a group of words in a fixed order, that have a particular meaning that is different from the meanings of each word on its own." [4]. In the Longman Idioms Dictionary (1998) the idioms are defined as "a sequence of words which has a different meaning as a group from the meaning it would have if you understand each word separately" [13]. The Dictionary of English Colloquial Idioms writes that "idioms are phrases which allow no elements to be replaced by a synonym" [25].

Consequently, idioms must not be broken up into their elements, as they are referred to as a fixed expression [5]. Brenner believes that native English speakers simply use idioms without being aware what constitutes them. He notices that in dictionaries certain confusion and disagreement can be found about the definition of idioms. However, the most usual definition is “two or more words together that, as a unit, have a special meaning, that is different from the literal meaning of the words separately.” These units sometimes are not only distinct in meaning from what the words would mean individually, but they are also considered more effective or thrilling in a certain context [2].

Idioms are an important and indispensable part of everyday language. They are considered a fascinating phenomenon in language and the interest in them has long tradition [3]. Levorato claims that the reason why they are so amazing is that they engage imagination, can transform abstract meaning into concrete ones and enrich the meaning of simple concepts. Idiomatic expressions are not a restricted part of the language, but they do exist in every area of human communication [14]. Johnson-Laird in 1993 describes idioms as mysterious as “the poetry of daily discourse”. They are universal, and this fact emphasizes even more their importance in language. Spontaneous speech becomes difficult without the use of idiomatic language [14, p.102].

The center in idioms studies has varied from form and frozenness to metaphoricity and the degree of literalness, i.e. from idiom structure to idiom meaning [17]. Different approaches and the variety of features of idioms have added to their complexity. According to Cacciari and Tabossi the difficulties in characterizing idioms is one of the reasons why idioms have reached fairly little attention even through their relevance is undisputable. Idioms are irrational and frustrating attribute of discourse since their meaning do not depend on the meanings of their parts and the syntactic relations of those parts [14].

3.2 Difficulties in Teaching-Learning English Idioms

The process of teaching and learning idioms has always been a challenging one. A teacher should have a well-founded knowledge of the language and its cultural aspects to search for the best meaning and decide when certain idioms would or would not be appropriate. So, a teacher usually develops different strategies and solutions regarding the teaching of idioms. In the literature of specialty there are described some features which can be responsible for the difficulties in idioms' teaching-learning.

Idioms are surely among the most difficult things for a person to acquire in the process of learning a new language, because people usually grow up using idioms. The English language itself possesses a huge variety of idioms, which infuse the language with taste and colour. Idioms are used in both spoken and written English, as well as, they are present in all spheres of life. They are better employed by native speakers, and a lot of linguists consider that idioms are just for one language, because in some cases, when an idiom is used

into a second language, its meaning may be misused or may have no sense as it once has in the source language.

Figurative meaning is the key feature of idioms, which V. V. Vinogradov named “the special chemical mixture” of the meaning of all components [23, p.123]. Consequently, idioms should be understood metaphorically rather than literally. That's why there is no surprise that in learning idioms, teachers run into difficulties that seem invincible.

The main problem the teachers face is the lack of equivalence. It means, that to find idioms in the target language which possess the same form and meaning as those in the source language, is almost impossible and leads to stylistic and semantic errors. The idioms that are culture bound are especially difficult to use. So, a teacher should proceed and explore patiently the culture of the target country in order to demystify and bring out cultural particularities strongly reflected in the language system. In short, the main problems that idioms raise in teaching relate to the following important fields: the ability to recognize and comprehend an idiom correctly; and the difficulties of reproducing the various aspects of meaning that an idiom brings into the target language. So, studying of idioms involves far more than the understanding of lexical and grammatical structures of two languages.

Moreover, problems of teaching-learning English idioms involve not only linguistic and stylistic features, but also the cultural and social differences between the original language and the second language.

Baker also refers to the difficulties in teaching-learning idioms. She underlines four main difficulties. The first is lack of an equivalent of an idiom or fixed expression in the studied language. The second difficulty noticed by Baker when an idiom has a similar counterpart in the second language, but it is used in different contexts because of its different meaning. The third type of problem occurs when “an idiom may be used in the native text in both its literal and idiomatic senses at the same time. And finally, the fourth difficulty mentioned by Baker is related to the different native-language and studied-language practice regarding the use of idioms in written text, certain contexts, or the frequency of their use [1, pp.10-75].

Davies as well mentioned some of the problems regarding the translation of idioms and fixed expressions, that are very similar to those noticed by Baker: recognition; lack of equivalent in second language; a similar counterpart in the studied language with a different context use; an idiom used in the native text both in its literal and idiomatic sense at the same time; difference between the agreement, context, and frequency of use in the studied language and native language [6].

According to all these challenging factors in recognizing, comprehension and learning idioms listed above, we can come to the conclusion that idioms are definitely a prominent field for teachers. Overall, there are some general features that make the process of teaching-learning idioms troublesome. In order to overcome these difficulties and to choose the right strategy of teaching, a teacher should know these characteristics of idioms that make them so challenging and complex.

So, the difficulties in studying English idioms are related to the complexity of their definitions and the understanding of their meaning.

3.2.1 The Complexity of the structure of Idioms

Idioms studies have a long way all over the world. But, despite the increased number of researches on idioms, scholars have not been able to agree on definition of them. Anyway, what is agreed on is that idioms are very difficult to characterize and, as Mantyla points out, it is impossible to define them in an undeniable way [17, p.36]. Moreover, to make this issue more difficult, one also has to differentiate idioms from idiomaticity. Fernando declares that idioms and idiomaticity are not identical even if they have close relations. She also claims that all idioms indicate idiomaticity, but not all words combinations that show idiomaticity are idioms. Fernando gives examples of word combinations, such as “catch a bus/a train” and “black/strong coffee”, that show idiomaticity but they aren’t idioms since they are quite unrestricted in their variants [8, p.30]. The parts of idioms cannot be changed or they can be replaced only within limitations. So, the essential characteristics of idioms should be explored in order to understand better their complex nature.

Mantyla is of the opinion that the character, range of literalness and figurativeness as well as the relationship between them appears to be the key point with idioms, because it is difficult to define the relationship of idioms with other metaphorical and multi-word expressions. However, he thinks that there are also other features of idioms that have been pointed out, such as their structure, for instance. The definition of the idiom depends on the feature that is emphasized. Some features of idioms are more valuable than others, but there must be involved many characteristics in order to call an expression an idiom [17, pp. 26-28].

By Fernando, there are three features that identify the idioms: structure, institutionalization and semantic opacity. Structure means that idioms consist of more than one word, so they are multiword expressions. Institutionalization denotes that idioms are conventionalized expressions as they are “created” word combinations. Semantic opacity refers to their non-literal features, namely the meanings of idioms are not the sum of their literal parts. Yet, Fernando admits that these three characteristics occur very habitually in many types of multi-word expressions, which means that such expressions as proverbs, collocations and similes can also be classified as idioms. Consequently, there have to be also some other features that differentiate idioms from other similar expressions [8, pp. 3-6].

Fernando’s definition of idioms is quite broad: “conventionalized multi-word expressions often, but not always, non-literal.” According to her the basis of idiomaticity is the habitual circumstances of specific words which conducts to the formation of different kinds of idioms and collocations. She differentiates between idioms and idiomaticity as well as idioms and collocations. Not all the word combinations that indicate idiomaticity are idioms, as well as, idioms and collocations are related, but still, different lexical types. Idioms require a specific order and lexical form. So

Fernando indicates three sub-classes of idioms: pure idioms, semi-idioms and literal idioms [8, p.38].

Afterwards, Mantyla refers to five features while characterizing idioms, which are: metaphoricity/figurativeness, analyzability/non-compositionality, fixed form, level of formality and multi-word expressions. Metaphoricity is the most common one and it is regarded as the essential feature of idioms. Analysability indicates that an idiom is dead, i.e. their meanings are arbitrary and not figurative. Steadiness of form, on the other hand, means that idioms do not tolerate any change in their structure, that they are frozen. The level of formality denotes that idioms belong to informal, spoken language. And finally, idioms imply more than one word, so, they are surely multi-word expressions [17].

However, later on, Mantyla disputes these views on the basis of other idiom studies and each feature is critically reviewed. So, all in all, he remarks that instead of the significance or degree of any single characteristic, idioms should comprise the combination of these features. None of the characteristics specified above may be used individually to identify an expression as an idiom [17].

During times, idioms have been explored from many different approaches, that have affected the definition of this term. Mantyla, consequently, introduces five different approaches that refer to idioms [17]:

1. The structure of an idiom and its variations.
2. The processing and storing of idioms.
3. The metaphoricity of idioms.
4. Teaching, learning and understanding idioms.
5. Idioms within idiomatic language, and the functions of idioms.

Uriel Weinreich in his study “Problems in the Analysis of Idioms” mentions two problems one should face while identifying idiomaticity:

- The first problem is to distinguish idioms from non-idiomatic expressions.
- The second one is to find out idioms that can be broken up into non-idiomatic components.

He writes that the semantic structure of idioms is “an extreme example of contextual semantic specialization, defined by a cluster of characteristics that also occur separately”. Later on, he refers to the definition of idioms, that are phraseological units which have at least two polysemous constituents, and in which there is a reciprocal contextual selection of sub-senses. He concentrates too much on form instead of meaning [24, pp. 40-43].

Fraser studied the meaning of idioms within the structure of the sentence, and how idioms can undergo particular syntactic transformation. He defines an idiom as “a constituent or series of constituents for which the semantic interpretation is not a compositional function of the formatives of which it is composed” [10]. He comes to the conclusion that idioms have the same deep structure analysis as their literal counterparts.

Makkai distinguishes between two types of idioms – lexemic and sememic. He declares that an idiom is made up of more than one free form and gives two features: lexemic idiom is defined as “each component can

occur in other environments as a realization of a monolexemic lexeme” and sememic idiom as “the aggregate literal meaning as derived from the respective constituent lexemes works additionally as a realization of a sememic network which is unpredictable”. He shows lexemic idioms with the example of “White House” and “blackbird” and sememic idioms with “chew the fat”. He also differentiates some types of idioms such as for example lexical clusters (red herring) or tournures (fly off the handle). His taxonomy of idioms is very effective and elaborated [16, pp. 101-120].

If to refer to some modern approaches to the complex problem of defining the idioms, F. R. Palmer is one of the foremost semanticists in the world, who has dealt with idioms in his book “Semantics”. He sees idioms as a collocation of a special kind and defines it as “a sequence of words whose meaning cannot be predicted from the meanings of the words themselves” [20, p.80]. He considers idiom semantically a single unit, but which do not function that way. Grammatically, on the other hand, idioms are not single units, mainly because they can't have a past tense as well as they can't sometimes form a passive voice (e.g. to kick the bucket – the bucket was kicked). In addition, there is a lot of other grammatical restrictions, that vary from idiom to idiom. Palmer calls these kind of idioms, frozen. Next, he refers to partial idioms, that are combinations of words where “one of the words has its usual meaning, the other one has a meaning that is peculiar to the particular sequence” [20, p.81]. For example, “red hair” that refers to hair, although the hair isn't strictly red in colour; or “white wine”, when the wine is in fact yellow by colour [20].

F. R. Palmer is also concerned with the phrasal verbs, that are the most commonly used idioms in English. He says that they are combinations “whose meaning cannot be predicted from the individual verb and adverb, and in many cases there is a single verb with the same or a very close meaning” [20, p.80-82]. Not all phrasal combinations have idiomatic status, many of them have a literal meaning, too. A very significant note in his work is about the translation of idioms. He says that a direct translation of idioms into other languages is in most cases not possible, and that for a successful translation, a translator has to find an equivalent of the idiom in the second language or rephrase the section involving idiom in different words [20].

Later on, C. Fernando and R. H. Flavell, in their book “On Idiom: Critical Views and Perspectives”, develop a complex, modern and innovative definitions of idioms, which is considered a turning point in phraseology. Their definition includes important extra-phraseological factors such as pragmatics and variability of fixedness. They consider that idioms cannot be described by one generally applicable feature, but rather “by multiple criteria, each criterion representing a single property” [7, p.49]. So, they describe idioms in terms of five features each idiomatic construction should have: its meaning isn't a sum of its constituents, it is institutionalized, it is transformationally deficient in one way or another, it forms part of a set of expression in given language and it is a unit that has a homonymous literal counterpart or individual components that

are literal, yet the expression as a whole would not be interpreted literally [7].

L. Lipka describes idioms as “formally complex lexemes that cannot be broken down into morphemes”, he adds that “if the semantic changes are so extreme that the meaning of the whole lexeme can no longer be derived from its parts, we speak of an idiom” [15, p.95]. Lipka claims that idioms are not “a simple, homogeneous category” and that “syntagmas of various kind are more or less affected by idiomaticity in the process of lexicalization” [15, p.96]. Consequently, idioms have a form of a single compounds (call girl, holiday), collocations (black market, red herring) or complex expressions (kick the bucket, blow a raspberry).

In 2009, in his book “Semantics”, J. I. Saeed distinguishes the idioms and the collocations. Collocations are “a restricting influence, the tendency for words to occur together repeatedly, ... (they) can undergo a fossilization process until they become fixed expressions” [21, p.60], for example, “powerful car”, “strong arguments”. Idioms, on the other hand, undergo a similar process of fossilization, and are “expressions where individual words have ceased to have independent meaning” [21, p.60], for example, “kith and span” or “spith and span”. He totally ignores expressions that are considered idioms by other linguists, for example “kick the bucket”. He also gives a different definition of idioms and states that individual words in idiom do not have their own meaning. That is a point of view that other scholars would clearly not support [21].

Therefore, according to the approaches to idiomaticity discussed above, we can definitely claim that the problem of idioms is a very difficult and complex one.

3.2.2 On Idiom Comprehension

Besides complex structure, the comprehension of idioms is another difficult moment in the process of teaching-learning English idioms.

Gibbs points in his study that idiom comprehension is a complicated matter [11, pp. 465-466, 470]. By his opinion, the literal meaning of idioms is not assessed at the same time as their idiomatic meaning, but the last is understood more or less directly. He considers that this is very important since many idioms don't have precise literal meaning. Gibbs also claims that idioms have different and more exact meanings than their literal counterparts [11, p. 494]. For instance, the literal paraphrase “to get very angry” is not as colourful and complex in meaning as its idiomatic expression “to blow your stack” [11, p. 504].

Idioms are not arbitrary, dead metaphors, but they “have complex figurative interpretations” [11, p. 485]. People are not aware of the origins of idioms and, therefore, it is considered that they are understood similarly as words [11, p. 58]. He admits that the use of idioms is a matter of convention. People usually learn their meanings without knowing where they originate from. However, Gibbs mentions, that it doesn't mean that idioms with highly conventionalized meanings are metaphorically dead [11, p. 60].

Later on, Cacciari and Tabossi suggested another hypothesis for idioms understanding. They consider that idioms don't exist distinct in mental lexicon and

their meanings are tied to certain strings of words, and the meanings are recognized after the sufficient input of the string is provided. Additionally, they claim that words in the lexicon are only in one form and they are not evaluated as literal or idiomatic [3, p. 678].

Comprehension of idioms that have literal and idiomatic meaning depends on when the idiomatic construction is accessible. Thus, idioms are strings of words and the idiomatic form is activated despite the key position.

In 1993 Flores d'Arcais declared that unfamiliar idioms require additional processing whilst highly familiar ones are understood easily. He also argues that even familiar idiomatic phrases are processed through a full syntactic analysis like any other linguistic structure [9, p. 97].

The way idioms are processed is not the only thing that affects their comprehension. There are some more factors that influence the interpretation process, such as familiarity and transparency of idioms, as well as the context.

Moon in his studies came up to the conclusion that figurative meanings of familiar idioms are processed more quickly than the familiar literal meanings [18, p. 139]. Thus, idioms that are unfamiliar and have low ratings in literalness are problematic in interpretation.

Nippold and Rudzinski also studied idiom comprehension and they noticed that familiarity and transparency had a significant effect on understanding. High-familiar idioms were usually less problematic to explain or understand than low-familiar idioms [19, p. 731-736]. Later on, Nippold and Taylor proved that familiarity and transparency of idioms are important factors in idioms understanding and explanation [19, p. 430]. So, they affect the process of comprehension of idioms, consequently, transparency and familiarity are key factors in acquisition and usage of idioms [19].

In addition to these, the context also plays a considerable role in idiom comprehension. According to Levorato studies, the linguistic context in which an idiom is fixed has an important role in the acquisition of the ability to understand idioms, since it offers the needed semantic background [14, p. 108]. She also investigated the role of familiarity in comparison with the role of context and concluded that familiarity increases the effect of context. Within literal contexts unfamiliar idioms are comprehended literally less often than familiar idioms. Thus, familiarity does have an effect with context, since it's easier to understand familiar idioms when they can associate the figurative meaning to some occasion they have already met [14, p. 113-115]. She also claims that comprehension is not an "all-or-none" process [14, p.106]. It relies on different factors such as the requirements of the task, previous knowledge and the ability to analyze language, and, as a result, it takes place in several different depths and levels. Figurative competence is the result of linguistic development and only very competent speakers have acquired this skill [14, p.104].

4. Discussion

So, the learning and teaching idioms are both difficult and complex, especially for second language learners. Irujo has noticed some reasons why idioms are

so difficult for second language learners [12, pp. 236-238]. Firstly, the non-literalness of idioms is confusing as most of idioms have literal counterparts. It is difficult for second language learners to discover which meaning is meant, the literal or idiomatic, especially when the idiom is not familiar to the learner. Comparatively, native speakers usually understand immediately which meaning is intended. Next, the problem is the lack of exposure to idioms. Irujo points out that idioms are commonly used in television or books, it means learners get in touch with them in non-interactive situations and consequently, they don't have the possibility to ask what these expressions mean or get any feedback on their own usage [12, p.237]. This brings us to the next problem: the correct use of idioms in appropriate situations in correct forms. Many idioms have grammatical constrains and can be used only in certain forms and they don't tolerate much variation. Furthermore, learners often try to connect to their native language while using idioms, which often leads to incorrect and comical expressions. Finally, Irujo names the lack of sufficient teaching materials as a significant difficulty in the process of idioms acquisition [12, p.237].

Later on, Sornig refers to the fact that even native speakers are unconfident when using the idioms and make mistakes. Idioms are so unique that there cannot be given any clear rules regarding their acquisition. According to Soring, the studying of idioms should begin from the point of view of native speakers and how they learn to understand them. Idioms are usually remembered because they are impressive in a situational way and communicatively effective. Sornig claims that learning a language means that one learns to deal with communicative situations, so learning idioms should be approached by categorizing them according to their communicative functions [22, p.286]. After all, the reason for the use of idioms is, surely, to bring colour and expressiveness to communicative interaction. So, it is clear, that whilst studying a foreign language, idioms should be acquired. But the only question is which ones Irujo noticed that often used, short and simple, and quite transparent idioms are the best known idioms. On the other hand, the least known idioms are less used, informal and included complex vocabulary [12].

Consequently, there is no point in trying to teach or learn rare, highly colloquial idioms that have difficult vocabulary. Furthermore, Irujo proposes that studying the understanding of idioms should prepare skilled learners to use the context in guessing the meaning and to handle figurative language generally. Later on, Irujo names more clearly the factors that should be considered in acquirement of idioms: frequency of use, transparency, appropriateness, form and vocabulary simplicity and similarity to first-language idioms [12, p. 238]. Irujo points out that the learning of idioms is essential for vocabulary practice of a second language [12, p.240].

Learners of English language are very interested in and enchanted of idioms, but they are often afraid of using them since figurative language is an area of language that causes difficulties. Nevertheless, proper strategies and methods of teaching-learning should be used in order to introduce idioms to a second language

learner, so that they can get rid of idiom-phobia and carry on acquiring idioms outside the classroom. On the whole, the acquisition of idioms requires complex linguistic and cognitive skills, that means more than merely passively learning distinctive words or phrases.

5. Conclusions

We all know that, nowadays, the use of English language has become a constituent part of our lives and as a result the teaching-learning of English becomes an essential activity because of the need to deal with people who speak differently. Therefore, during this investigation of the theoretical basis of the process of teaching-learning the English idioms, we have come to the conclusion that idioms are an incontestable part of English language, which are to be learned and used as they make a language more colourful and interesting to discover. For the reason that idioms are a part of metaphorical language, which has a surface as well as a deep meaning, they are difficult for foreign learners who are not familiar with them. Studying idioms, in fact, is a very interesting process in spite of the difficulties and obstacles that the teacher is likely to come across during it. These problems are generally due to the differences between the languages involved at different levels. In this respect, many different scholars analyze the reasons behind the idiom-phobia. We have also tried here to analyze and then summarize the most common considerations of the difficulties in teaching-learning the English idioms. Consequently, we can notice that the complex structure and the lack of equivalence (or comprehension) are the main reasons that make idiom acquisition troublesome. And, we consider that the awareness of these causes could be of great help in teaching-learning process of English language. Finally, we find that further research on overcoming difficulties in teaching-learning English idioms would be an interesting topic as idioms are the taste and colour of a language.

References

1. Baker, M. In *Other Words: A Course Book on Translation*, Routledge: London, UK, 1992, 390 p.
2. Brenner, G. A. *American Idioms Handbook*, Webster's New World Book: Massachusetts, USA, 2003, 480 p.
3. Cacciari, C.; Tabossi, P. *Idioms. Processing, Structure and Interpretation*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates: Hillsdale, NJ, USA, 1993, pp. 102-145.
4. Cambridge Dictionary. Available online: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org> (accessed on 05.03.2023).
5. Cowie, A. P.; Mackin, R.; McCaig, R. *Oxford Dictionary of Current Idiomatic English: Verbs with Prepositions and Particles*, Oxford University Press: Oxford, UK, 1975, Volume 2, 685 p.
6. Davies, M. In *Touch. Course 4: A Word of Difference*, WSOY: Porvoo, Finland, 1996, pp. 120-146.
7. Fernando, C.; Flavell, R. *On Idioms: Critical Views and Perspectives*. Exeter Linguistic Studies: Exeter, UK, 1981, 5, 221 p.
8. Fernando, C. *Idioms and Idiomaticity*. Penguin books, London, UK, 1996, 265 p.
9. Flores d'Arcais, G. B. *The Comprehension and Semantic Interpretation of Idioms*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Hillsdale, NJ, USA, 1993, p.81.
10. Fraser, B. *Idioms Within a Transformational Grammar*. *Foundations of Language* 1970, 6, pp. 22-42.
11. Gibbs, R. W. Jr. *Spilling the Beans on Understanding and Memory for Idioms in Conversation*. *Journal of Memory & Cognition* 1980, 8, pp. 149-156.
12. Irujo, S. *A Piece of Cake: Learning and Teaching Idioms*. *ELT Journal* 1986, 3, pp. 236-242.
13. Laurence, U. A.; Thomas, H. L. *Longman Dictionary of English Idioms*, 1st ed.; Longman Publishing Group: London, UK, 2000, 412 p.
14. Levorato, M. C. *The Acquisition of Idioms and the Development of Figurative Competence*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates: Hillsdale, NJ, USA, 1993, pp.101-128.
15. Lipka, L. *An Outline of English Lexicology*. Max Niemeyer Verlag, Tübingen, Germany, 1990, 225p.
16. Makkai, A. *Idiom Structure in English*. Mouton, The Hague, Netherlands, 1972, 371 p.
17. Mantyla, K. *Idioms and Language Users: The Effect of the Characteristics of Idioms on Their Recognition and Interpretation by Native and Non-native Speakers of English*, University of Jyväskylä: Jyväskylä, Finland, 2004, 239 p.
18. Moon, R. *Fixed expressions and Idioms in English*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK, 1998, 338 p.
19. Nippold, M. A.; Rudzinski, M. *Familiarity and Transparency in Idiom Explanation: A development Study of Children and Adolescents*. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Research*, 1993, 2, pp. 728-737.
20. Palmer, F. R. *Semantics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1981, 232 p.
21. Saeed, J. L. *Semantics*. Wiley-Blackwell, London, UK, 2009, 597 p.
22. Sornig, K. *English Idioms in Language Teaching*. Max Niemeyer, Tübingen, Germany, 1988, p. 38-45.
23. Vinogradov, V. A. *On Idioms*, Nauka: Moscow, Russia 1990, pp. 120-171
24. Weinreich, U. *Problems in the Analysis of Idioms*. *Journal of Puhvel* 1969, 2, pp. 23-81.
25. Wood, F. T.; Hill, R. J. *Dictionary of English Colloquial Idioms*, MacMillan: London, UK, 1979, 354p.